

5th

European

★ Conference on ★
Pharmaceutics

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Ready for the future: innovative dosage forms and
advanced technologies for modern therapeutics

Porto Portugal
24 - 25 March 2025

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5th European Conference on Pharmaceutics

Innovative dosage forms and advanced technologies for modern therapeutics

24 - 25 March 2025, Porto, Portugal

Dear Colleague,

Following the great success of the past European Conferences on Pharmaceutics, which were held in Reims, Krakow, Bologna and Marseille, it is our great pleasure to announce the fifth congress of this series of international meetings, which will be organised in Porto, Portugal, on 24-25 March 2025. It will be dedicated to "Innovative dosage forms and advanced technologies for modern therapeutics".

The European Conferences on Pharmaceutics are held every two years (in March/April of the uneven years). They are jointly organized by the APGI ("International Society of Drug Delivery Sciences and Technology"), APV ("International Association for Pharmaceutical Technology") and SITELF ("Italian Society of Pharmaceutical Technology and Legislation and Related Disciplines").

Generally, about 600 participants join the conference. Often, one third of them come from industry, one third have permanent position at academia, and one third are young scientists: PhD students & postdocs - the next generation of researchers in our field. The aim is to help bridging the gap between fundamental academic research and industrial applications, offering the opportunity to initiate fruitful exchange and cooperation between university and industry. The conference will be a perfect occasion for young as well as established scientists from all over the world to present their work, discuss most recent scientific findings, network and to share their experience with colleagues. World-wide leading experts in the field will give plenary lectures and invited talks on hot topics. They will give overviews on the current state of the art in the respective domains and outlooks on future perspectives. In addition, new research findings will be presented in the form of short talks, selected from submitted abstracts. Furthermore, poster presentations will give the opportunity to get an update on the most recent discoveries in pharmaceutics and to personally exchange with the authors.

An industrial exhibition will accompany the conference and allow learning about the current trends and newest products in the areas of pharmaceutical ingredients, analytical technologies, equipment, medicinal products, medical devices, contract manufacturing and many other fields.

Please note that all coffee and lunch breaks as well as the welcome reception will be included in the registration fees and will be held in the industrial exhibition & poster presentation area in order to facilitate discussions between participants, exhibitors and presenters.

We are very much looking forward to welcoming you to the 5th European Conference on Pharmaceutics in Porto in 2025!

Juergen Siepmann
President APGI

Sandra Klein
President APV

Paola Minghetti
President SITELF

Chair and programme committee

Chair of the conference

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Impact of Selected Surfactants and Polymers on the Stability and Rheological Characteristics of Zinc Oxide Suspensions for Topical Use

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INTRODUCTION

According to The European Pharmacopoeia (11th Edition), liquid preparations for dermal use are intended for application to the skin to deliver active substances for local or systemic effect (1). Suspensions are distinguished within this general monograph. A well-formulated suspension may develop a sediment that can be easily re-dispersed upon shaking, restoring the formulation to a stable, homogeneous state suitable for consistent drug delivery. The suspension should possess an appropriate viscosity that would retard the sedimentation of the solid phase, without hindering the application process, in addition to having favorable sensory and textural attributes. Physical instability is a major challenge in the development of novel formulations. The use of polymers offers a rational strategy to address this issue, due to their multifunctionality as flocculants, wetting agents and viscosity-enhancing agents. This study aimed to evaluate the impact of the selected polymers on the qualitative and rheological characteristics and physical stability on the model of zinc oxide suspension for dermal application.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Thirteen formulations of 15% zinc oxide (ZnO) suspension (*Suspensio album 15%*) were compounded in accordance with the guidelines from the *Magistral Formulae 2008* of the Republic of Serbia (2). An official suspension of zinc oxide with talc and twelve modified suspensions containing either polysorbate 20 (P20), polysorbate 60 (P60) or polysorbate 80 (P80) (0.05% or 0.5% m/m) combined with sodium carboxymethylcellulose (NaCMC) (0.25% or 0.5% m/m) were prepared. The visual characteristics and pH values of the formulations were recorded. Sedimentation coefficients (S_q) were calculated at specified time points up to seven days at 25°C, as well as after thermal and gravitational stress tests, to assess physical stability. Redispersion time and flow rate were measured. Flow curves were obtained and amplitude sweep and frequency sweep tests performed to analyze the rheological properties of the prepared suspensions.

RESULTS

The principal objective of this study was to access the influence of P20, P60 and P80 (0.05% and 0.5%), in addition to NaCMC (0.25% and 0.5%) on the qualitative characteristics, rheological profiles and physical stability of the ZnO suspensions. Aforementioned excipients, at the specified concentrations, function as wetting i.e. suspending agents and viscosity enhancers. Furthermore, they are characterized by a high degree of compatibility with the other formulation components, as well as a favorable safety profile.

Visual characteristics and pH

Visual inspection indicated that the inclusion of the selected excipients did not significantly alter the organoleptic qualities of the ZnO suspensions, which remained white, odorless and homogenous. The pH values of the formulations ranged from 9.00 (for the control) to 9.51 (for 0.5% P60+0.5% NaCMC), suggesting that the addition of the polymers only slightly increased the pH value of the model suspension whose alkaline properties can be attributed to the inherent quality of ZnO.

Physical stability

After two hours, sedimentation was observed only in the control suspension. However, after 24 hours, only 0.05%P20+0.25%NaCMC, 0.05%P20+0.5%NaCMC, 0.05%P60+0.5%NaCMC and 0.5%P60+0.5%NaCMC remained completely dispersed, while the phase separation was the most evident in 0.5%P80+0.5%NaCMC. After 7 days, all formulations exhibited S_q values equal to or greater than control ($S_q=0.9$), with the exception from 0.5%P80+0.5%NaCMC characterized by the lowest $S_q=0.8$. Thus, all of the formulations, except from the latter, demonstrated satisfactory physical stability for the compounded suspensions. Redispersion times for all formulations were shorter (15-56 s) compared to the control (60 s), except from the 0.5%P80+0.5%NaCMC (68 s). These results suggest that the addition of NaCMC retarded sedimentation of the solid phase by increasing the viscosity of the medium, while the sediment remained loosely packed,

facilitating redispersion. This effect may be attributed to the wetting properties of polysorbates.

In terms of stability under stress testing, the control suspension ($Sq=0.48$) exhibited the highest stability under gravitational stress, with significant phase separation observed in all other formulations (Sq range 0.12–0.36). However, under temperature stress conditions, the control suspension experienced significant sedimentation ($Sq = 0.43$), while no such phase separation was observed in the other formulations (Sq range 0.98–1.00).

Flow rate and rheological properties

The incorporation of polymers led to a decrease in the flow rates of the suspensions compared to the control, attributable to the increase in viscosity. Flow curve analysis demonstrated that all formulations exhibited pseudoplastic flow behavior (Figure 1), which is desirable for topical applications. The polymer concentration had the most significant impact on the degree of deviation from Newtonian flow, consistent with findings reported in the literature. Oscillatory rheological measurements revealed that the loss modulus (G'') consistently exceeded the storage modulus (G') in all suspensions, indicating their predominantly viscous nature (Figures 2a and 2b). Moreover, higher concentrations of NaCMC resulted in increased G' and G'' values, reflecting a higher gel-like structure. The critical shear stress values also increased with polymer concentration, suggesting a greater resistance to disruption of the internal suspension structure.

Figure 1. Flow curves of the suspensions

Figure 2a.

Change in elastic (G') and viscous modulus (G'') values of selected suspensions depending on shear stress

Figure 2b.

Change in elastic (G') and viscous modulus (G'') values of selected suspensions depending on the frequency at constant shear stress within the linear viscoelastic region

CONCLUSIONS

Examination of the organoleptic properties of the modified zinc oxide suspension formulations revealed that the addition of polysorbates and sodium carboxymethylcellulose did not affect the color, odor, or homogeneity of the suspensions. The prepared formulations demonstrated excellent physical stability, as indicated by the sedimentation coefficients, and exhibited improved redispersibility compared to the control formulation. These findings suggest that the incorporation of wetting agents and the increase in viscosity positively influenced the quality of the suspensions. Furthermore, the addition of the excipients significantly enhanced the formulations' resistance to temperature stress, although the effect was less pronounced under gravitational stress conditions.

The inclusion of the polymeric excipients also led to an increase in the apparent viscosity of the suspensions, as reflected by a decrease in flow rate. All polymer-containing formulations exhibited pseudoplastic flow, a desirable characteristic for topical preparations, along with a broader linear viscoelastic region compared to the control. The rheological properties of the suspensions were primarily influenced by the concentration of cellulose derivatives.

These results suggest potential for further research into the modification of official suspension formulations, exploring the use of alternative polymers and their combinations with surfactants to optimize both the physical stability and rheological properties of the formulations.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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